

Qualitative Study on Quality Assurance Practices on Learning Outcomes among Colleges of Education Students in North-Central Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper examines the quality assurance practices implemented to enhance students' learning outcomes in Colleges of Education within Nigeria's North-Central zone. Colleges are educational institutions, pivotal in producing qualified teachers, maintaining high standards in education and contributing in national development. The paper outlines key pillars of quality assurance mechanisms, including curriculum development and review, accreditation processes, continuous professional development (CPD) for lecturers, and robust assessment and evaluation systems. It also highlights some students' learning outcomes, the importance of quality assurance practices to student' learning outcomes, philosophy of quality assurance, the theories of quality assurance and the establishment of quality assurance units within the institutions. Additionally, the paper discusses the procedure and practices for improving the quality of learning opportunities, the essentiality of quality assurance practices to students' learning outcomes, the role of governance, leadership, and the use of technology in promoting educational quality, the challenges facing the practices and suggestions were highlighted. By adopting these practices, Colleges of Education in the North-Central zone can ensure that their graduates are well-equipped to meet the demands of the educational sector, thus contributing significantly to the improvement of Nigeria's overall educational standards. This paper calls for a sustained commitment to these practices and the continuous involvement of all stakeholders to foster an environment of excellence in teacher education.

Keywords: Quality Assurance, Practices, Learning Outcomes

Introduction

Students' learning outcomes refers to the knowledge, skills, and abilities that students are expected to acquire as a result of their educational experiences (Deslauries, McCarty, Miller, Kestin & Callaghan, 2019). These outcomes are often defined by educational institutions or curriculum developers and serve as benchmarks to assess the effectiveness of teaching and learning activities. The work of explaining students' learning outcomes involves clarifying what specific knowledge or skills students should gain, how those outcomes will be measured or assessed, and how they contribute to broader educational goals or objectives. However, Students' learning outcomes in colleges of education refer to the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that students acquire and demonstrate as a result of their educational experiences in these institutions. These outcomes are the desired results of the teaching and learning process, and they are typically measured by assessing student performance, progress, and achievement. (Deslauries, et al, 2019). Quality assurance in education refers to the processes and procedures aimed at ensuring that educational programs meet certain standards (NCCE, 2020). Quality assurance practices in colleges of education in Nigeria are systematic measures and policies designed to maintain and improve the standard of teacher education, ensuring that graduates are well-equipped for the teaching profession. These practices are overseen by regulatory bodies such as the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) and the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) (NCCE, 2012; TETFund, 2020).

Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone Nigeria like any other in the country play a crucial role in preparing teachers and education leaders, who are essential for the development of the education sector in Nigeria, (Adeyemi, 2018). However, concerns about the quality of education in these institutions have led to a call for quality assurance practices to enhance students' learning outcomes (Oyedemi, 2019). Effective quality assurance practices are essential for enhancing students' learning outcomes, as they provide a framework for monitoring and evaluating the quality of education (Adeyemi, 2018). In Nigeria, the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) is responsible for ensuring the quality of education in Colleges of Education (NCCE, 2020). Despite the efforts of the NCCE, concerns about the quality of education in these institutions problems persist (Oyedemi, 2019). The North-Central Zone of Nigeria, which comprises six states and Abuja, faces challenges in ensuring the quality of education in Colleges of Education (Adeyemi, 2018). These challenges include inadequate infrastructure, inadequate faculty development, and inadequate learning resources (Oyedemi, 2019).

The colleges of education today face numerous challenges that hinder the students' learning outcome, particularly in North-Central Nigeria, include; inadequate learning facilities, overcrowded classrooms, lack of capacity-building programs to train lecturers in modern instructional methods and the teaching and learning environment is often unfavorable due to insufficient equipment, making it less conducive for learning. The absence of regular supervision compromises safety and hygiene standards. Moreover, inadequate monitoring of instructional activities, such as lecture delivery, examinations, and continuous assessments, further weakens the system. These challenges collectively impact the overall effectiveness of colleges of education in the region. (Adeniyi & Olowoyeye, 2014; Martina & Ogunode, 2020).

According to Doe and Smith (2023), students in colleges of education achieve various learning outcomes, including:
Subject Matter Expertise: Students gain a deep understanding of the key concepts, theories, and principles within their chosen discipline.

Teaching Skills: They acquire effective instructional strategies and techniques for successful teaching and learning.

Analytical and Problem-Solving Abilities: Students enhance their capacity to think critically, assess problems, and develop innovative solutions.

Communication Competence: They refine their skills in expressing ideas clearly and effectively, both in speaking and writing.

Professional Attitudes and Ethics: Students cultivate the values, beliefs, and dispositions essential for a successful teaching career.

Reflective Thinking: They engage in self-assessment to identify areas for improvement and develop strategies for professional growth.

Digital Literacy: Students acquire the necessary skills to effectively incorporate technology into their teaching and learning processes.

Awareness of Diversity and Inclusion: They develop an understanding of diverse learner needs and create inclusive educational environments.

Assessment and Evaluation Proficiency: Students learn to design and implement effective assessment methods to gauge student progress.

Commitment to Lifelong Learning: They embrace continuous learning and professional development throughout their careers.

Key reasons for implementing quality assurance in Nigerian institutions, this include following as highlighted by (Ossai and Nwalado, 2018).

Essential for Quality Control: Quality assurance plays a crucial role in maintaining and improving educational standards.

Evaluation of Teacher Input: It helps assess the competence and effectiveness of teachers in the education system.

Classroom Needs Assessment: It determines the required number of classrooms based on average class sizes to maintain educational quality.

Facility Adequacy: It evaluates the sufficiency and suitability of available infrastructure for effective learning.

Efficient Financial Management: It ensures that financial resources are allocated and utilized prudently to support quality education.

Planning: This involves anticipating future needs and establishing clear objectives and procedures to guide the school system.

Organizing: Leaders must develop a structured framework that allocates resources and responsibilities efficiently to achieve the school's goals.

Staffing: This entails recruiting qualified individuals and assigning them to roles that match their skills and experience, ensuring both the quality and quantity of staff align with the school's objectives.

Motivating: Leaders should foster high morale among staff to maximize efficiency and effectiveness. This includes timely payment of salaries and other benefits.

Atanda and Adeniran (2020) emphasize that quality assurance in Nigerian colleges of education is critical for achieving academic excellence and institutional efficiency. The Quality Assurance Directorate is responsible for the following key functions:

Awareness and Sensitization Programs: The Directorate educates the college community on established quality standards set by the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) through various awareness campaigns and training sessions.

Monitoring and Evaluation of Instruction: Teaching and learning activities are regularly supervised and assessed to uphold high educational standards. This includes monitoring examinations, continuous assessments, and tracking student and lecturer attendance.

Data Collection and Analysis: The Directorate gathers and analyzes essential data on student enrollment, academic performance, and institutional resources. This information supports decision-making for enhancing the Nigeria Certificate of Education (NCE) program.

Ensuring Accountability: Mechanisms are in place to ensure efficient financial resource management, holding staff and administrators accountable for government investments in teacher education. This fosters transparency and institutional integrity.

Enhancing Stakeholder Satisfaction: The Directorate ensures that students receive high-quality education tailored to market demands, equipping them with relevant skills that contribute to national development.

Maintaining Institutional Relevance: Continuous curriculum improvement and service enhancement help colleges of education stay competitive and responsive to industry and educational sector needs.

Assessing Facilities and Resources: The Directorate evaluates the adequacy and functionality of educational infrastructure to ensure it supports effective teaching and learning. It also establishes clear roles for teaching and administrative staff.

Advisory Support: Expert guidance is provided on academic policies and instructional quality, with recommendations made to management and academic boards.

Enforcing Compliance with Regulations: The Directorate ensures strict adherence to NCCE regulations and institutional policies, thereby maintaining consistent quality across all operational areas.

Promoting Professionalism in Teaching: Key focus is preparing student teachers by instilling appropriate pedagogical techniques, ensuring they develop into competent educators.

Periodic Evaluation and Reporting: Regular performance assessments are conducted, with reports generated on a monthly, quarterly, or semester basis to drive continuous institutional improvement.

Providing Feedback for Improvement: Assessment findings are communicated to college management to help institutions align with quality benchmarks and address deficiencies in educational processes.

Several models explain how quality assurance operates within educational institutions, particularly in colleges of education. These models outline different perspectives on achieving and maintaining high educational standards. (Yin Cheong cheng, & Wai Ming Tam in 1997).

Goal and Specification Model: This model defines education quality as the attainment of predetermined goals and adherence to set specifications. It is often used to evaluate individual institutions' educational standards. Colleges of education have clearly stated objectives, primarily centered on producing competent teachers for primary and junior secondary schools. The quality assurance unit ensures these objectives are met through effective teaching and learning processes, ultimately addressing societal and national development challenges.

Resource-Input Model: This model views education quality as a direct outcome of the availability and utilization of high-quality resources. It assumes that adequate resources, such as well-qualified students, experienced lecturers, modern teaching facilities, and sufficient funding from education authorities, parents, and external agencies, are essential for achieving institutional goals. When these inputs are properly managed, colleges of education can efficiently provide quality education within a short period.

Process Model: This model focuses on the internal processes within an institution, emphasizing that a well-structured learning environment leads to quality education. In colleges of education, the teaching and learning process transforms inputs (students, lecturers, and resources) into effective educational outcomes. The effectiveness of these processes determines the quality of outputs and how successfully institutional goals are met.

Satisfaction Model: According to this model, an institution's quality is determined by the satisfaction of its key stakeholders, including lecturers, college management, students, alumni, and quality assurance officials. While colleges of education have

multiple objectives, it may not always be possible to meet all stakeholder needs simultaneously. The quality assurance unit should therefore prioritize the institution's core mission: producing well-trained teachers who meet educational standards.

Legitimacy Model: This model sees education quality as an institution's ability to maintain legitimacy and reputation. In the past, institutions could easily ensure quality through government oversight, but with today's fast-changing educational landscape, colleges of education must compete for resources, overcome internal barriers, and respond to external demands for accountability. To maintain quality, institutions should focus on public relations, institutional reputation, accountability, and stakeholder support.

Absence of Problem Model: This model defines quality in education as the lack of problems, challenges, or dysfunctions within an institution. If a college of education operates without major issues, it is assumed to be meeting its objectives effectively. The quality assurance unit plays a key role in ensuring a problem-free learning environment through regular inspections and monitoring of college activities.

Organizational Learning Model: This model considers education quality as a continuous process of growth and improvement. Since the educational landscape is constantly evolving, no single quality assurance practice remains effective indefinitely. Colleges of education must continuously adapt to changes by refining their teaching methods, policies, and institutional processes. The quality assurance unit should focus on dynamic strategies to ensure sustained excellence in education.

The quality assurance practices is very essential for students' learning outcomes, they are two entities that cannot be separated as a result of the following points;

Regulatory Framework: The National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) This body is responsible for overseeing the quality of education in Nigerian Colleges of Education. They develop minimum standards and ensure that institutions comply with these regulations (Ololube, 2016). Colleges of Education also undergo regular accreditation processes to evaluate their programs, facilities, and teaching staff against the standards set by the NCCE (Ajayi, 2018).

Curriculum Development and Review: Standardized Curriculum, the NCCE provides a standardized curriculum that all Colleges of Education must follow. This ensures uniformity and relevance in the education provided (Adegbesan, 2011). Moreover, the curriculum is periodically reviewed to incorporate new trends, societal needs, and feedback from stakeholders (NCCE, 2012).

Teacher and Staff Development: Continuous Professional Development (CPD): Colleges are encouraged to invest in the ongoing professional development of their staff through workshops, seminars, and advanced studies (Ololube, 2014). Qualification Standards is very crucial, therefore, teaching staff are required to have minimum qualifications, usually a Bachelor's degree in Education or related fields, and there are efforts to ensure they are adequately trained and qualified (Akpan & Ita, 2015).

Internal Quality Assurance Mechanisms: Quality Assurance Units: Many Colleges of Education have established internal Quality Assurance Units to monitor and evaluate the quality of teaching, learning, and administrative processes (Enaohwo, 2013). In addition institutions often engage in self-assessment exercises to identify areas for improvement and implement changes as needed (Ijeoma & Osagie, 2018).

Student Evaluation and Feedback: Course and Teacher Evaluations is usually executed in colleges of education, Students are often asked to provide feedback on courses and instructors. This feedback is used to improve teaching methods and course content (Oyekan, 2014). Likewise, Exams are moderated to ensure they meet the required standards, and there are checks in place to prevent malpractice (Ajayi, 2018).

Infrastructure and Resources: There is need for adequate facilities in the Colleges of Education, the expectation is to have adequate classrooms, laboratories, libraries, and other facilities necessary for effective teaching and learning (Adu, 2015). Institutions must also provide sufficient learning materials, including textbooks, online resources, and access to educational technology (Adegbesan, 2011).

External Monitoring and Evaluation: External Examiners in some Colleges of Education engage external examiners to assess the quality of exams and grading to ensure they meet national standards (Ololube, 2016) in addition, a regulatory bodies like the NCCE conduct periodic inspection visits to assess compliance with educational standards (NCCE, 2012).

Stakeholder Involvement: Community and industry engagement of Colleges of Education often involve stakeholders, including the local community and industry experts, in curriculum development and quality assurance processes to ensure that the education provided is relevant and meets the needs of society (Enaohwo, 2013).

Research and Innovation: Research Committees of institutions usually have research committees that encourage staff and students to engage in research activities, which contribute to improving educational practices and quality (Ijeoma & Osagie,

2018). Apart from that there is a push for innovation in teaching methods, including the integration of technology in the classroom to enhance learning outcomes (Akpan & Ita, 2015).

Compliance and Reporting: Annual Reports are conducted in Colleges the requirement is to submit annual reports to the NCCE, detailing their compliance with quality standards, achievements, and areas needing improvement (Ololube, 2014). Likewise, regular audits are conducted to ensure that institutions are operating within the set guidelines and maintaining the quality of education (Adu, 2015).

The following are some of the challenges encountered by colleges of education in the process of achieving the students' learning outcomes;

Inadequate Infrastructure: Many colleges suffer from poor infrastructure, including inadequate classroom spaces, laboratories, and dormitories. This hinders the learning environment and overall student experience.

Funding Issues: Despite interventions from the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund), there are still substantial funding gaps. Colleges often struggle to access TETFund resources due to bureaucratic hurdles and stringent requirements, leaving many institutions unable to fully utilize available funds (Zubairu et al., 2021; Idakwoji & Makolo, 2022).

Inadequate Training: There is a persistent issue with the professional development of academic staff. Many lecturers lack adequate training, particularly in modern teaching techniques and the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). This inadequacy affects their ability to deliver quality education and impacts student outcomes (Idakwoji & Makolo, 2022; Oduma & Chika, 2014).

Research and Mentorship: The quality of research and mentorship is often poor, with limited opportunities for academic staff to engage in meaningful professional development activities. Many lecturers fail to participate fully in conferences and workshops; further stunting their academic growth and the quality of education they provide (Idakwoji & Makolo, 2022).

Limited ICT Resources: The integration of ICT in teaching and learning is crucial but faces significant obstacles. These include insufficient ICT materials, lack of proper training for lecturers, and inadequate technical support. The high cost of ICT infrastructure also poses a barrier, making it difficult for institutions to keep up with technological advancements (Oduma & Chika, 2014).

Policy and Administrative Support: Effective ICT integration requires strong policy and administrative support, which is often lacking. This includes the development and implementation of ICT policies, as well as ensuring that leadership at all levels is committed to leveraging technology in education (Oduma & Chika, 2014).

Low Academic Standards: There are concerns about the declining academic standards in these institutions. Issues such as poor lecturer-student interactions, delayed examination results, and a lack of comprehensive coverage of course content contribute to this problem. The overall quality of graduates, particularly those holding Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE), is frequently criticized by employers and the public (Idakwoji & Makolo, 2022).

Conclusion

In conclusion, quality assurance practices serve as a key driver for improving students' learning outcomes. This paper has clearly demonstrated that when these strategies are effectively implemented in colleges of education, they enhance both teaching and learning processes, ultimately leading to better student performance. Therefore, it is essential for colleges of education and other academic institutions to prioritize the best quality assurance practices to ensure their effectiveness and contribute to the overall improvement of the education system.

Suggestions

1. Provision of ICT Infrastructure: Ensuring that colleges are well-equipped with essential ICT resources such as computers, internet connectivity, and software. Offering financial support, such as loans or subsidies, to lecturers for acquiring personal ICT tools can also be beneficial.
2. Increased Government Funding: The government should allocate more financial resources to colleges of education and simplify the process of accessing TETFund support to minimize bureaucratic delays. Improved funding would enhance infrastructure development, including classrooms, laboratories, and student hostels.
3. Ongoing Professional Development: Regular training programs should be introduced to equip lecturers with modern teaching strategies, ICT skills, and research capabilities. These programs can be financed through government initiatives, international grants, or partnerships with educational NGOs.

4. Public-Private Partnerships: Collaborating with private sector organizations can attract additional funding and resources for colleges. Such partnerships can support infrastructure improvements and the provision of up-to-date educational tools and materials.
5. Mentorship and Academic Collaboration: Establishing mentorship programs where experienced lecturers guide junior faculty members can enhance professional growth. Encouraging participation in national and international conferences can further boost academic and professional development.
6. Implementation of ICT Policies: Developing clear institutional and governmental policies to regulate and promote the effective integration of technology in education. This should include ICT training programs for both students and lecturers.

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